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THETIDA: THE EUROPEAN PROJECT FOR THE PRESERVATION OF UNDERWATER AND COASTAL CULTURAL HERITAGE

The Horizon Europe funded project THETIDA, designed for the preservation of underwater and coastal cultural heritage, held its first plenary meeting on the 7th of November, to provide partners with the opportunity to exchange and learn more on the project's latest advancements.

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EURISY for the THETIDA Project

On November 7th, 2023, THETIDA partners gathered online for the project first plenary meeting, scheduled exactly six months after the kick-off event in Vouliagmeni (Greece). Representatives of the 17 Consortium partners participated to showcase the diverse advancements of the project and discuss next actions to ensure the achievement of its goals. This event was also an opportunity to acknowledge the project “development phase” inception, as mentioned Panagiotis Michalis, THETIDA project coordinator from ICCS (Institute of Communication and Computer Systems).

The technologies and methodologies developed within THETIDA aim at providing cutting-edge solutions to safeguard Europe underwater and cultural heritage. The overarching methodology developed is based on a holistic approach, bringing together scientific and technical innovations, including latest citizens science and crowdsourcing tools, that ensure a seamless connection between experts, local authorities, and citizens to better monitor, prevent and preserve underwater and coastal heritage.

Quoting the Project Coordinator, Dr Angelos Amditis:

“I am thrilled to take the opportunity to address the project’s interdisciplinary team of researchers, experts, and practitioners who will develop, test, and validate an integrated multiple heritage risk assessment and protection system with evidence-based monitoring frameworks, innovative tools and instruments.”

To establish solid interconnections and socio-economic models adapted to the specificities of every pilot site, and likely to be scaled-up and used in other cultural heritage sites, THETIDA research institutions are identifying and analysing stakeholders and end-users needs, requirements, and best practices. THETIDA research partners are composed of high-ranking universities, such as the University of Padova (Italy), the Technical University of Eindhoven (the Netherlands), the National Technical University of Athens (Greece), and the University of Algarve (Portugal), that combine their expertise to provide prime data to the project.

Setting the foundations of THETIDA’s development phase, the first maps of Mykonos coastline, using and processing datasets from Copernicus satellite Sentinel-2 complemented with Landsat-5 data, have been provided. By accentuating and superimposing maps from 1984 to today, THETIDA partners will have a precise overview of the changes in the coastline, as results of coastal erosion, among other factors, and will be able to produce rigorous predictive maps to identify areas subject to coastal deterioration as well as sites at risk. Technical partners also identified three types of land deformation patterns in Svalbard using SAR (Synthetic Aperture Radar) altimetry data. This active data collection method allows for a better understanding of surfaces characteristics, which is relevant to appreciate soil structure and to estimate permafrost degradation. Thanks to the SAR altimetry data collected and processed, partners will develop a prediction tool to calculate relative coastal deformation and inundation.

To complement Earth Observation and Remote Sensing techniques, a new generation of AUVs (Autonomous Underwater Vehicles), with a variety of adapted sensors are being developed and will be tested in two of THETIDA underwater pilot sites: La Spezia (Italy) and Algarve (Portugal). AUVs are part of an ensemble of six other in-situ equipment that will be developed within the project and tested in its diverse pilot sites, according to the needs of each pilot sites, and include wearable sensing devices for divers, smart buoys, sensors to be mounted on local fishermen boats, smart tags mounted on coastal cultural heritage sites, and micro weather stations. The improved AUVs will supply detailed geometry of the sites and surrounding ocean bottom, which are crucial elements to model underwater cultural heritage. To reinforce the models, the AUVs will also collect environmental variables, and will be used to compare models and real observations.

The combination of spatial and in-situ data will give to THETIDA a unique and accurate understanding of underwater and coastal heritage deterioration, useful to create an integrated multiple Heritage Risk Assessment and Protection System.

The plenary was also the occasion to inform the partners on the latest scientific advancements, mostly related to the collection and testing of archaeological material samples from pilot sites, that are crucial to identify the effects of different forms of degradation, including degradation of submerged materials and the impact of the sea-spray wetting phenomena on materials vulnerability.

In the spirit of this multidisciplinary project, partners update each other on the activities aimed at bridging gaps between different potential end-users communities, such as experts, administrators,

and citizens. Combining crowdsourcing, and citizens science tools, a mobile app will be created. Building on the CircularAR app, one of the results of HYPERION project, THETIDA aims to extend its current functionalities to capture and upload data on smartphones. To enhance end-users' experiences related to cultural heritage on site, online, and at home, THETIDA's developers will implement augmented reality overlays, guided tours, visual detection capabilities to interact with the environment, and incorporate gamification techniques to encourage active participation. This enhanced mobile app will allow for end-users to educate themselves on THETIDA's approach and will also be used to collect cultural heritage sites data.

“By collaborating closely with other THETIDA partners, we aim to collect as many inputs as possible and to display them in a fun and gamified way. Imagine how your perception of climate change could change, if you were able to witness the sea level rise and the coastal erosion taking place in front of you through your smartphone camera?”

- Tina Katika, developer of the THETIDA mobile app (ICCS)

To conclude, THETIDA's partners developed the so-called *Living Labs* methodology to enable the co-creation of cultural heritage innovative preservation solutions addressing the actual needs of users. Living Labs work as multi-stakeholders' platforms and interaction spaces in which interested actors meet, discuss natural hazards impacts, and design together future scenarios and roadmaps to ensure the resilient future of vulnerable underwater and coastal heritage sites. The first Living Lab has been tested in the IJsselmeer area (the Netherlands) and will be equally applied to all the other pilot sites in the months to come: La Spezia and Gallinara (Italy), Algarve (Portugal), Svalbard (Norway), Mykonos (Greece), and Paralimni (Cyprus).

About the THETIDA Project:

THETIDA is a European Union funded project that kicked-off in May 2023, online, and will be funded until October 2026. The 17 Consortium partners, composed of an interdisciplinary team of researchers, experts and practitioners, aim at developing cutting-edge technical, scientific and impact-oriented solutions to safeguard and preserve Europe's coastal and underwater cultural heritage from climate change and natural hazards.

The THETIDA project is driven by a holistic approach that addresses risk management, protection and preparedness, as complementary strategies to prevent damages to cultural heritage sites, identify and ward off additional threats and promote policy tools for climate neutrality and economic resilience in coastal areas.

The next plenary meeting will take place in La Spezia, Italy, in June 2024.

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